

ISic4401

I.Sicily inscription 4401

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halicyae

Place of origin (modern)

Salemi

Provenance

panel preserved from a later mosaic floor on top of two earlier layers, this mosaic A, in the paleo-Christian basilica first excavated by Salinas in 1893

Coordinates

37.833019, 12.808066

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Salemi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

tessillis

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---]cd[---]a [te]mporibus
2. [---]o in Dom(ino) cd [---][po]ntificis patris episoc(opi)
3. [---]xitus su[---]io[[]][D]ominus do
4. [---]en[---][h]onoris se
5. [---][sancte ecclesie ca]tolice

Apparatus

Text of Rizzone

Rizzone suggests alternatively: [sancte fidei ca]tolice

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

- Pace, B. 1916. La basilica di Salemi. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 697-736. At 702 no.1
- Bilotta, M. 1977. Le epigrafi musive della basilica di S. Miceli di Salemi. *FR*. 31-64. At 34-36
- 1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1028
- undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 341
- Rizzone, V.G. 2011. Opus Christi edificabit: stati e funzioni dei cristiani di Sicilia attraverso l'apporto dell'epigrafia (secoli IV-VI). *Documenti e studi di Synaxis* 25. Troina. At 81 A13

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